

Experiment Design for Data Science

Exercise 2: Reproduce experimental results:

Understanding COVID-19 News Coverage using Medical NLP - Group 45

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ABSTRACT

The publication includes references to the code that was used to replicate the experiment. These references in many cases may or may not be included in different papers, depending on where you obtain them. Despite code being available, reproducing the results seems to be challenging. This is because the code is inadequately documented. Also, we used a dataset that was obtained from scraping the data from CNN and The Guardian and compared the results with the actual ones from the paper. All these results will be further explained in addition.

KEYWORDS

NLP, COVID-19, Natural Language Processing, Reproducibility

1 INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 was first reported in December 2019. Because it has a highly contagious nature, it quickly spread throughout the world, until the World Health Organization (WHO) declared this virus outbreak as global pandemic [1]. News coverage played a key role to help public understanding of the risk, measures to limit

disease spread, and political and policy discourses.

This study uses over 36,000 articles from live blogs and key moments reported by CNN and The Guardian published between 2020 and 2021. COVID-19 has been studied before including news coverage, but this study is unique in applying healthcare-specific deep learning networks, models, and embeddings enabling the extraction and correlation of over 100 diverse types of medical entities with high accuracy.

This paper uses clinical and biomedical NLP models from the Spark NLP for Healthcare library. NLP is built on top of Apache Spark which enables implementation of recent NLP algorithms and models for deep learning. This library provides implementation on various programming languages such as Java, Python, Scala, or R. Study uses fine-tuned NLP models to find the most frequent COVID-19 symptoms, variants, and prevention guidelines, finds the most affected countries, population groups and profession and compares unstructured text with reported WHO statistical data, among others.

The authors of research showed that the countries with most COVID reported cases were USA, India and Brazil and the number of patients who died were among these countries.

The most mentioned age group was 60+ years old and the most mentioned professions after healthcare professionals, who were understandably first, were researchers, workers, teachers, and government officials. The analysis shows that the total number of cases and deaths reported by the news are mostly consistent with the numbers shared by WHO officially

Coughing, blood clotting, sneezing, fatigue, shortness of breath, and headache are the prevailing COVID-19 symptoms. However, specific symptoms related to loss of smell and taste are also observed, although their frequency is lower.

Figure 1 shows the Top 10 treatments, symptoms, drugs, and procedures in the order of their frequencies. Overall, reported numbers by CNN and The Guardian about deaths and infections are correlated with the WHO official data. NLP models performed well on extraction of the terms from the source.

treatments	treatment occurrence	symptoms	symptom occurrence	drugs	drug occurrence	procedures	procedure occurrence
wear masks	1842	cough	243	pfizer and biontech	584	intubation	67
isolation	777	blood clot	214	astrazeneca	275	inoculations	33
quarantine	658	sneeze	97	hydroxychloroquine	228	dialysis	18
vaccination	563	confusion	90	moderna	131	resuscitation	12
oxygen support	482	fatigue	86	chloroquine	57	bypass	10
ventilators	445	shortness of breath	63	novavax	57	autopsies	9
social distancing	342	headache	57	sanofi	49	organ transplants	8
intensive care	248	flu-like symptoms	56	tamoxifen	49	cpr	7
the pfizer/biontech vaccine	161	unwell	50	sinovac	40	hand washing	4
self-isolate	136	anger	49	hand sanitizer	31	gtr	3

Figure 1: Top 10 Treatments, Symptoms, Drugs, and Procedures

2 REPRODUCIBILITY

The code was available by the authors and accessible as a Jupyter Notebook and it can be

downloaded from GitHub. Although the experiment stages are detailed in the study, it is not stated which set-up was used, such as the operating system or Python version. Paper scraped dataset from CNN and The Guardian, but this process was outdated. The data collection procedure was updated due to the references of web scrapers in CNN and Guardian changing, resulting in a need for an updated approach. A new data source, Brazilian Report, was added to enrich the dataset for new findings and compare the results with dataset from mentioned news outlets.

This dataset appears to be a collection of news articles and key moments related to the coronavirus (COVID-19) from CNN's and The Guardian's liveblogs. The dataset is collected by web scraping CNN and The Guardian search results for the query "coronavirus news" and visiting the liveblog URLs returned. The dataset contains the title, text, date published, and URL of each article or key moment, along with a Boolean flag indicating whether the item is a key moment or not. The text of the articles and key moments is pre-processed, through the removal of special characters and lowercase all letters. The date is also formatted. The dataset is stored in lists of dictionaries. Dataset includes the live blogs of CNN and The Guardian from 22nd January 2020 and The Guardian from 24th January 2020 until the end of 2021.

The preprocessing steps include parsing HTML format, converting the dates, and extracting key moments from live blogs together with first date and last date created and amount of news. This script is performing preprocessing on a data frame of news articles, specifically cleaning the data by removing any rows that contain certain strings in the 'title' and 'text' columns, and

removing any duplicate rows based on the 'title', 'text', and 'date' columns. The cleaned data is then written to a Json file in the 'data clean' directory.

The data pre-processing was upgraded as there were many invalid references in the data but also the code was prone to duplicates and may be storing the same data multiple times if it runs repeatedly.

This leads to the next component, which is the implementation. As a result, we could not implement the code because it has many issues starting from the computational resources, license problems and finding alternative libraries to reproduce the results.

3 RESULTS

We encountered many problems and setbacks trying to reproduce the code and the results from the paper. We must say that the code and data are not well documented, and we had to try different platforms, approaches, and solutions to try and make the code work and below we have listed some of the problems and tried solutions:

- **Technical Challenges with Spark NLP JSL:** The team ran into problems while trying to run Spark NLP JSL and was unable to execute it on any of the platforms tested. We tried to run it locally on an M1 chip, Intel chip and we also tried Google Colab but neither of these were enough to make it work.
- **Alternative Libraries:** An attempt was made to find alternative libraries to reproduce the results but was not successful, and the team was unable to reproduce the part of finding a better correlation on the use cases of countries with less news coverage. However, based on data analysis, it was believed

that this would have been the case, as the entity of Brazil had significantly more occurrences in the new dataset.

- **Licensing Issues with Spark NLP JSP:** The team encountered licensing issues while trying to run Spark NLP JSP. The team checked if the license was still valid and made sure that the license was installed and properly configured but we could not overcome this problem, which hindered the progress further.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Regarding the dataset that was used to reproduce the experiment, the results were quite similar, however we believe that there are other datasets that would give better results according to the code that was available.

In the paper, the team highlighted several challenges to reproducibility in scientific research, including poor reporting of methods and results, selective reporting of results, and the use of inadequate sample sizes and libraries which are not publicly available.

We suggest several solutions, including improving the transparency of research, improving the standards for reporting and documenting methods and results, and increasing the incentives for reproducibility.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] W. H. Organization, et al., The corona virus disease 2019 (covid-19) (2020).
- [2]https://github.com/JohnSnowLabs/spark-nlp-workshop/blob/master/tutorials/academic/Text2Story_CEUR_Workshop_2022_April.ipynb
- [3] Ali Emre Varol , Veysel Kocaman , Hasham UI Haq and David Talby Understanding COVID-19 News Coverage using Medical NLP, Proceedings of Text2Story — Fifth Workshop on Narrative Extraction From Texts held in conjunction with the 44th European Conference on Information Retrieval (ECIR 2022) Stavanger, Norway, April 10, 2022.

